

Demographic, economic, geospatial data for municipalities of the Central Federal District in Russia (excluding the city of Moscow and the Moscow oblast) in 2010–2016

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Received 10 December 2019 ♦ Accepted 28 December 2019 ♦ Published 30 December 2019

Citation: Kalabikhina IE, Mokrensky DN, Panin AN (2019) Demographic, economic, geospatial data for municipalities of the Central Federal District in Russia (excluding the city of Moscow and the Moscow oblast) in 2010–2016. Population and Economics 3(4): 121–134. <https://doi.org/10.3897/popecon.3.e39152>

Keywords

Data base, demographic, economic, geospatial data

JEL Codes: J1, J3, R23, Y10, Y91

I. Brief description

The database contains demographic, economic, geospatial data for 452 municipalities of the 16 administrative units of the Central Federal District (excluding the city of Moscow and the Moscow oblast) for 2010–2016 (Appendix, Table 1; Fig. 1). The sources of data are the municipal-level statistics of Rosstat, Google Maps data and calculated indicators.

II. Data resources

Data package title: Demographic, economic, geospatial data for municipalities of the Central Federal District in Russia (excluding the city of Moscow and the Moscow oblast) in 2010–2016.

Figure 1. Map of studied administrative units and municipalities. *Source:* constructed by the authors

Resource link: <https://zenodo.org/record/3590379#.Xgp1979S814>

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3590379

Data format: xlsx, shape-files

Description:

The data can be downloaded from the online database Demographic, economic, geospatial data for municipalities of the Central Federal District in Russia (excluding the city of Moscow and the Moscow oblast) in 2010–2016.

The data files MUNICIPALITIES_CFD_RUSSIA.zip (16 MB) consists of:

1) MUNICIPALITIES_CFD_Russia_2010_2016_ENG.xlsx – The database of demographic, economic, geospatial data for 452 municipalities of the 16 administrative units of the Central Federal District in Russia (excluding the city of Moscow and the Moscow oblast) for 2010-2016.

2) MUNICIPALITIES_CFD_RUSSIA_SHAPE.rar – The shape-files for maps construction,

3) Fig.1. Municipalities ENG.jpg – The map of studied administrative units and municipalities of the Central Federal District in Russia.

III. Structure and methodology of data collection

The database contains demographic, economic, geospatial data for 452 municipalities of the 16 administrative units of the Central Federal District (excluding the city of Moscow and the Moscow oblast) for 2010–2016.

Excluding municipalities of the city of Moscow and the Moscow oblast from the database is due to the fact that the Moscow agglomeration is so specific in its economic and demographic development (Shatokhin and Tinkova 2010). In addition, the change of borders of the city of Moscow and the Moscow oblast in 2011–2012 requires a separate study of these regions in the period under consideration (2011–2016). (Makhrova and Kirillov 2018).

The sources of data are the municipal-level statistics of Rosstat, Google Maps data and calculated indicators. The statistical data were arranged by the year, the data on municipalities for which there were administrative and territorial transformations for the period under study were excluded (in some cases, the data were provided in accordance with the administrative-territorial demarcation as of 2016).

Municipalities' websites were used to fill the lack of population information in individual municipalities for some years.

Calculated variables were made to estimate a number of indicators per capita, to introduce additional demographic indicators (e.g. migration inflow rate), to bring price economic indicators to base year prices (2010). For example, indicators of income of the local budget, volumes of investments in fixed assets (excluding budgetary funds), level of wages are modified to a comparable form (to 2010 prices).

The distances on roads in different units of measurement from the geographical center of municipalities to the center of the capital of the region are calculated using the Google Maps database.

Data mapping was performed using ArcGIS software.

Some publications are connected with the database (and its extended version): (Kalabikhina et al. 2018), (Mokrensky 2018), (Kalabikhina and Mokrensky 2017).

IV. Data sources

Municipal-level statistics of Rosstat (The Russian Federal State Statistics Service), municipalities' websites, Rosstat data on the consumer price index for goods and services, Google Maps data. Data sources and data description see (Appendix, Table 2).

V. Brief demographic information on the Central Federal District of the Russian Federation

It is the largest in population federal district of Russia, where a quarter of its population is concentrated. Administrative units of the Central Federal District present the "most demographically depressive" regions of Russia (The Concept... 2009). According to official statistics, within 27 years after the USSR collapsed, the population of Russia decreased by 2.3% (excluding the population of the Republic of Crimea), and the population of the territory of the Central Federal District (excluding the city of Moscow and the Moscow oblast) decreased by 13.1%.

VI. Contributions to the creation and development of the database:

Idea, structure, description of the database — Doctor in Economics Irina Kalabikhina.

Collection, calculation, description of demographic and economic data, registration of the Russian patent for the first version of the database (Mokrensky 2019) — Denis Mokrensky.

Collecting geospatial data, shape-files, maps — PhD Aleksandr Panin.

Database support and development: all authors.

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Appendix

Table 1. List of administrative units and municipalities of the Central Federal District in Russia (excluding the city of Moscow and the Moscow oblast).

Name of the region of the Russian Federation	Name of the municipality	Name of the region of the Russian Federation	Name of the municipality
Belgorod Oblast	Alekseevsky municipality	Ryazan Oblast	Aleksandro-Nevisky municipality
Belgorod Oblast	Belgorodsky municipality	Ryazan Oblast	Chuchkovsky municipality
Belgorod Oblast	Borisovsky municipality	Ryazan Oblast	city of Kasimov
Belgorod Oblast	Chernyansky municipality	Ryazan Oblast	city of Ryazan
Belgorod Oblast	city of Belgorod	Ryazan Oblast	city of Sasovo
Belgorod Oblast	city of Starooskolsky	Ryazan Oblast	city of Skopin
Belgorod Oblast	Grayvoronsky municipality	Ryazan Oblast	Kadomsky municipality
Belgorod Oblast	Gubkinsky municipality	Ryazan Oblast	Kasimov municipality
Belgorod Oblast	Ivnyansky municipality	Ryazan Oblast	Klepikovskiy municipality
Belgorod Oblast	Korochansky municipality	Ryazan Oblast	Korablinsky municipality
Belgorod Oblast	Krasnensky municipality	Ryazan Oblast	Mikhailovsky municipality
Belgorod Oblast	Krasnogvardeysky municipality	Ryazan Oblast	Miloslavsky municipality
Belgorod Oblast	Krasnoyarskiy municipality	Ryazan Oblast	Pitelinsky municipality
Belgorod Oblast	Novooskolsky municipality	Ryazan Oblast	Pronsky municipality
Belgorod Oblast	Prokhorovsky municipality	Ryazan Oblast	Putyatinsky municipality
Belgorod Oblast	Rakityansky municipality	Ryazan Oblast	Ryazansky municipality
Belgorod Oblast	Rovensky municipality	Ryazan Oblast	Ryazhskiy municipality
Belgorod Oblast	Shebekinsky municipality	Ryazan Oblast	Rybnovskiy municipality
Belgorod Oblast	Valuysky municipality	Ryazan Oblast	Sapozhkovskiy municipality
Belgorod Oblast	Veydelevsky municipality	Ryazan Oblast	Saraevsky municipality
Belgorod Oblast	Volokonovsky municipality	Ryazan Oblast	Sasovskiy municipality
Belgorod Oblast	Yakovlevsky municipality	Ryazan Oblast	Shatsky municipality
Bryansk Oblast	Brasovskiy municipality	Ryazan Oblast	Shilovskiy municipality
Bryansk Oblast	Bryanskoye municipality	Ryazan Oblast	Skopinsky municipality
Bryansk Oblast	city of Bryansk	Ryazan Oblast	Spasskiy municipality
Bryansk Oblast	city of Fokino	Ryazan Oblast	Starozhilovskiy municipality
Bryansk Oblast	city of Klintsy	Ryazan Oblast	Ukholovskiy municipality
Bryansk Oblast	city of Novozybkov	Ryazan Oblast	Yermishynskiy municipality
Bryansk Oblast	city of Seltsa	Ryazan Oblast	Zakharovskiy municipality
Bryansk Oblast	city of Starodub	Smolensk Oblast	city of Desnogorsk
Bryansk Oblast	Dubrovskiy municipality	Smolensk Oblast	city of Smolensk
Bryansk Oblast	Dyatkovskiy municipality	Smolensk Oblast	Demidovskiy district
Bryansk Oblast	Gordeevskiy municipality	Smolensk Oblast	Dorogobuzhskiy municipality
Bryansk Oblast	Karachevskiy municipality	Smolensk Oblast	Dukhovshchinskiy municipality
Bryansk Oblast	Kletnyanskoye municipality	Smolensk Oblast	Gagarinskoye municipality
Bryansk Oblast	Klimovskiy municipality	Smolensk Oblast	Glinkovskiy municipality
Bryansk Oblast	Klintsovskiy municipality	Smolensk Oblast	Holm-Zhirkovskiy municipality
Bryansk Oblast	Komarichskiy municipality	Smolensk Oblast	Kardiyevskiy municipality

Name of the region of the Russian Federation	Name of the municipality	Name of the region of the Russian Federation	Name of the municipality
Bryansk Oblast	Krasnogorsky municipality	Smolensk Oblast	Khislavichy municipality
Bryansk Oblast	Mglinsky municipality	Smolensk Oblast	Krasninsky municipality
Bryansk Oblast	Navlinsky municipality	Smolensk Oblast	Monastyrshinsky municipality
Bryansk Oblast	Novozybkovsky municipality	Smolensk Oblast	Novoduginsky municipality
Bryansk Oblast	Pochepsky municipality	Smolensk Oblast	Pochinkovsky municipality
Bryansk Oblast	Pogarsky municipality	Smolensk Oblast	Roslavlsky municipality
Bryansk Oblast	Rognedinsky municipality	Smolensk Oblast	Rudnyansky municipality
Bryansk Oblast	Sevsky municipality	Smolensk Oblast	Safonovsky municipality
Bryansk Oblast	Starodubsky municipality	Smolensk Oblast	Shumyach municipality
Bryansk Oblast	Surazhsky municipality	Smolensk Oblast	Smolensky municipality
Bryansk Oblast	Suzemsky municipality	Smolensk Oblast	Sychevsky municipality
Bryansk Oblast	Trubechevsky municipality	Smolensk Oblast	Temkinsky municipality
Bryansk Oblast	Unechansky municipality	Smolensk Oblast	Ugransky municipality
Bryansk Oblast	Vygonichsky municipality	Smolensk Oblast	Velyzhsky municipality
Bryansk Oblast	Zhiryatinsky municipality	Smolensk Oblast	Vyazemsky municipality
Bryansk Oblast	Zhukovsky municipality	Smolensk Oblast	Yartsevsky municipality
Bryansk Oblast	Zlynkovsky municipality	Smolensk Oblast	Yel'ninsky municipality
Ivanovo Oblast	city of Ivanovo	Smolensk Oblast	Yershichsky municipality
Ivanovo Oblast	city of Kineshma	Tambov Oblast	Bondarsky municipality
Ivanovo Oblast	city of Kohma	Tambov Oblast	city Kirsanov
Ivanovo Oblast	city of Shuya	Tambov Oblast	city of Kotovsk
Ivanovo Oblast	city of Teykovo	Tambov Oblast	city of Michurinsk
Ivanovo Oblast	city of Vichuga	Tambov Oblast	city of Morshansk
Ivanovo Oblast	Furmanovsky municipality	Tambov Oblast	city of Rasskazovo
Ivanovo Oblast	Gavrilovo-Posadsky municipality	Tambov Oblast	city of Tambov
Ivanovo Oblast	Il'insky municipality	Tambov Oblast	city of Uvarovo
Ivanovo Oblast	Ivanovsky municipality	Tambov Oblast	Gavrilovsky municipality
Ivanovo Oblast	Kineshemy municipality	Tambov Oblast	Inzhavinsky municipality
Ivanovo Oblast	Komsomolsky municipality	Tambov Oblast	Kirsanovsky municipality
Ivanovo Oblast	Lezhnevsky municipality	Tambov Oblast	Michurinsky municipality
Ivanovo Oblast	Lukhsky municipality	Tambov Oblast	Mordovsky municipality
Ivanovo Oblast	Palekhsky municipality	Tambov Oblast	Morshansky municipality
Ivanovo Oblast	Pestyakovsky municipality	Tambov Oblast	Muchkapsky municipality
Ivanovo Oblast	Privolzhsky municipality	Tambov Oblast	Nikiforovsky municipality
Ivanovo Oblast	Puchezhsky municipality	Tambov Oblast	Pervomaisky municipality
Ivanovo Oblast	Rodnikovsky municipality	Tambov Oblast	Petrovsky municipality
Ivanovo Oblast	Savinsky municipality	Tambov Oblast	Pichaevski municipality
Ivanovo Oblast	Shuisky municipality	Tambov Oblast	Rasskazovsky municipality
Ivanovo Oblast	Teikovsky municipality	Tambov Oblast	Rzhaksin municipality
Ivanovo Oblast	Verkhnelandekhovsky municipality	Tambov Oblast	Sampursk municipality
Ivanovo Oblast	Vychugsky municipality	Tambov Oblast	Sosnovsky municipality
Ivanovo Oblast	Yurievetsky municipality	Tambov Oblast	Staroyuryevsky municipality
Ivanovo Oblast	Yuzhsky municipality	Tambov Oblast	Tambovsky municipality
Ivanovo Oblast	Zavolzhsky municipality	Tambov Oblast	Tokarovsky municipality

Name of the region of the Russian Federation	Name of the municipality	Name of the region of the Russian Federation	Name of the municipality
Kaluga Oblast	Babyninsky municipality	Tambov Oblast	Umotsky municipality
Kaluga Oblast	Baryatinsky municipality	Tambov Oblast	Uvarovsky municipality
Kaluga Oblast	Borovsky municipality	Tambov Oblast	Zherdevsky municipality
Kaluga Oblast	city of Kaluga	Tambov Oblast	Znamensky municipality
Kaluga Oblast	city of Obninsk	Tula Oblast	Aleksinsky municipality
Kaluga Oblast	Duminichsky municipality	Tula Oblast	Arsenievsky municipality
Kaluga Oblast	Dzerzhinsky municipality	Tula Oblast	Belevsky municipality
Kaluga Oblast	Ferzikovsky municipality	Tula Oblast	Bogoroditsky municipality
Kaluga Oblast	Iznoskovsky municipality	Tula Oblast	Chernsky municipality
Kaluga Oblast	Khvastovichy municipality	Tula Oblast	city of Donskoy
Kaluga Oblast	Kirovsky municipality	Tula Oblast	City of Novomoskovsk
Kaluga Oblast	Kozelsky municipality	Tula Oblast	city of Tula
Kaluga Oblast	Kuibyshevsky municipality	Tula Oblast	Dubensky municipality
Kaluga Oblast	Lyudinovsky municipality	Tula Oblast	Efremovsky municipality
Kaluga Oblast	Maloyaroslavetsky municipality	Tula Oblast	Kamensky municipality
Kaluga Oblast	Medynsky municipality	Tula Oblast	Kimovsky municipality
Kaluga Oblast	Meshchovsky municipality	Tula Oblast	Kireevsky municipality
Kaluga Oblast	Mosalsky municipality	Tula Oblast	Kurkinsky municipality
Kaluga Oblast	Peremyshlsky municipality	Tula Oblast	Leninsky municipality
Kaluga Oblast	Spass-Demensky municipality	Tula Oblast	Novogurovsky urban locality
Kaluga Oblast	Sukhinichy municipality	Tula Oblast	Odoevsky municipality
Kaluga Oblast	Tarsky municipality	Tula Oblast	Plavsky municipality
Kaluga Oblast	Ulyanovsky municipality	Tula Oblast	Schekinsky municipality
Kaluga Oblast	Yukhnovsky municipality	Tula Oblast	Slavny urban locality
Kaluga Oblast	Zhukovsky municipality	Tula Oblast	Suvorovsky municipality
Kaluga Oblast	Zijdrinsky municipality	Tula Oblast	Teplo-Ogarevsky municipality
Kostroma Oblast	Antropovsky district	Tula Oblast	Uzlovsky municipality
Kostroma Oblast	Buysky municipality	Tula Oblast	Venevsky municipality
Kostroma Oblast	Chukhlomsky municipality	Tula Oblast	Volovsky municipality
Kostroma Oblast	city of Buy	Tula Oblast	Yasnogorsky municipality
Kostroma Oblast	city of Galich	Tula Oblast	Zaoksky municipality
Kostroma Oblast	city of Kostroma	Tver Oblast	Andreapolsky municipality
Kostroma Oblast	city of Manturovo	Tver Oblast	Belsky municipality
Kostroma Oblast	city of Sharya	Tver Oblast	Bezhetsky municipality
Kostroma Oblast	city of Volgorochensk	Tver Oblast	Bologovsky municipality
Kostroma Oblast	Galichsky municipality	Tver Oblast	city of Kimry
Kostroma Oblast	Kadyysky municipality	Tver Oblast	city of Rzhev
Kostroma Oblast	Kolhryvsky municipality	Tver Oblast	city of Torzhok
Kostroma Oblast	Kostromskoy municipality	Tver Oblast	city of Tver
Kostroma Oblast	Krasnoselsky municipality	Tver Oblast	city of Vyshniy Volochek
Kostroma Oblast	Makarievsky municipality	Tver Oblast	Firovsky municipality
Kostroma Oblast	Manturovsky municipality	Tver Oblast	Kalininsky municipality
Kostroma Oblast	Mezhevskoy municipality	Tver Oblast	Kalyazinsky municipality
Kostroma Oblast	Neisky municipality	Tver Oblast	Kashinsky municipality

Name of the region of the Russian Federation	Name of the municipality	Name of the region of the Russian Federation	Name of the municipality
Kostroma Oblast	Nerekhtsky municipality	Tver Oblast	Kesovogorsky municipality
Kostroma Oblast	Oktyabrsky municipality	Tver Oblast	Kimrsky municipality
Kostroma Oblast	Ostrovsky municipality	Tver Oblast	Konakovsky municipality
Kostroma Oblast	Parfenevsky municipality	Tver Oblast	Krasnokholmshsky municipality
Kostroma Oblast	Pavinsky municipality	Tver Oblast	Kuvshinovskiy municipality
Kostroma Oblast	Ponazyrevskiy municipality	Tver Oblast	Lesnoy municipality
Kostroma Oblast	Pyshchugskiy municipality	Tver Oblast	Likhoslavskiy municipality
Kostroma Oblast	Sharyanskiy municipality	Tver Oblast	Maksatikhinskiy municipality
Kostroma Oblast	Soligalichskiy municipality	Tver Oblast	Molokovskiy municipality
Kostroma Oblast	Sudislavskiy municipality	Tver Oblast	Nelidovskiy municipality
Kostroma Oblast	Susaninskiy municipality	Tver Oblast	Oleninskiy municipality
Kostroma Oblast	Vokhomskiy municipality	Tver Oblast	Ostashkovskiy municipality
Kursk Oblast	Belovskiy municipality	Tver Oblast	Penovskiy municipality
Kursk Oblast	Bolshesoldatskiy municipality	Tver Oblast	Rameshkovskiy municipality
Kursk Oblast	Cheremisinskoye municipality	Tver Oblast	Rzhevskiy municipality
Kursk Oblast	Chomutovskiy municipality	Tver Oblast	Sandovskiy municipality
Kursk Oblast	city of Kurchatov	Tver Oblast	Selizharovskiy municipality
Kursk Oblast	city of Kursk	Tver Oblast	Sonkovskiy municipality
Kursk Oblast	city of Lgov	Tver Oblast	Spirovskiy municipality
Kursk Oblast	city of Shchigry	Tver Oblast	Staritskiy municipality
Kursk Oblast	city of Zheleznogorsk	Tver Oblast	Toropetskiy municipality
Kursk Oblast	Dmitrievskiy municipality	Tver Oblast	Torzhokskiy municipality
Kursk Oblast	Fatezhskiy municipality	Tver Oblast	Udomelskiy municipality
Kursk Oblast	Glushkivskiy municipality	Tver Oblast	Vesyegonskiy municipality
Kursk Oblast	Gorshechenskoye municipality	Tver Oblast	Vyshnevolotskiy municipality
Kursk Oblast	Kastorenskoye municipality	Tver Oblast	Zapadnodvinskoye municipality
Kursk Oblast	Konyshovskoye municipality	Tver Oblast	Zharkovskoye municipality
Kursk Oblast	Korenevskoye municipality	Tver Oblast	Zubtsovskoye municipality
Kursk Oblast	Kurchatovskoye municipality	Vladimir Oblast	Aleksandrovskoye municipality
Kursk Oblast	Kurskiy municipality	Vladimir Oblast	city of Gus-Khrustalny
Kursk Oblast	L'govskiy municipality	Vladimir Oblast	city of Kovrov
Kursk Oblast	Manturovskoye municipality	Vladimir Oblast	city of Murom
Kursk Oblast	Medvenskiy municipality	Vladimir Oblast	city of Vladimir
Kursk Oblast	Oboyanskoye municipality	Vladimir Oblast	Gorokhovetskiy municipality
Kursk Oblast	Oktyabrskoye municipality	Vladimir Oblast	Gus-Khrustalny municipality
Kursk Oblast	Ponirovskoye municipality	Vladimir Oblast	Kameshkovskoye municipality
Kursk Oblast	Pristenskiy municipality	Vladimir Oblast	Kirzhachskiy municipality
Kursk Oblast	Rylskiy municipality	Vladimir Oblast	Kolchuginskiy municipality
Kursk Oblast	Shchigrovskoye municipality	Vladimir Oblast	Kovrovskoye municipality
Kursk Oblast	Solntsevskoye municipality	Vladimir Oblast	Melenkovskoye municipality
Kursk Oblast	Sovetskiy municipality	Vladimir Oblast	Muromskoye municipality
Kursk Oblast	Sujanskoye municipality	Vladimir Oblast	Petushinskoye municipality
Kursk Oblast	Timskiy municipality	Vladimir Oblast	Selivanovskoye municipality
Kursk Oblast	Zheleznogorskoye municipality	Vladimir Oblast	Sobinskoye municipality

Name of the region of the Russian Federation	Name of the municipality	Name of the region of the Russian Federation	Name of the municipality
Kursk Oblast	Zolotukha municipality	Vladimir Oblast	Sudogodsky municipality
Lipetsk Oblast	Chaplyginsky municipality	Vladimir Oblast	Suzdalsky municipality
Lipetsk Oblast	city of Chaplygin	Vladimir Oblast	Vyaznikovsky municipality
Lipetsk Oblast	city of Dankov	Vladimir Oblast	Yuriev-Polsky municipality
Lipetsk Oblast	city of Gryazi	Voronezh Oblast	Anninsky municipality
Lipetsk Oblast	city of Lebedyan	Voronezh Oblast	Bobrovsky municipality
Lipetsk Oblast	city of Lipetsk	Voronezh Oblast	Bogucharsky municipality
Lipetsk Oblast	city of Usman	Voronezh Oblast	Buturlinovsky municipality
Lipetsk Oblast	city of Yelets	Voronezh Oblast	city of Borisoglebsk
Lipetsk Oblast	city of Zadonsk	Voronezh Oblast	city of Novovoronezh
Lipetsk Oblast	Dankovsky municipality	Voronezh Oblast	city of Voronezh
Lipetsk Oblast	Dobrinsky municipality	Voronezh Oblast	Ertilsky municipality
Lipetsk Oblast	Dobrovsky municipality	Voronezh Oblast	Gribanovsky municipality
Lipetsk Oblast	Dolgorukovsky municipality	Voronezh Oblast	Kalachevsky municipality
Lipetsk Oblast	Gryazinsky municipality	Voronezh Oblast	Kamensky municipality
Lipetsk Oblast	Izmalkovsky municipality	Voronezh Oblast	Kantemirovsky municipality
Lipetsk Oblast	Khlevensky municipality	Voronezh Oblast	Kashirsky municipality
Lipetsk Oblast	Krasninsk municipality	Voronezh Oblast	Khokholsky municipality
Lipetsk Oblast	Lebedyansky municipality	Voronezh Oblast	Liskinsky municipality
Lipetsk Oblast	Lipetsky municipality	Voronezh Oblast	Nizhnedevitsky municipality
Lipetsk Oblast	Liv-Tolstovsky municipality	Voronezh Oblast	Novokhopersky municipality
Lipetsk Oblast	Stanovlyansky municipality	Voronezh Oblast	Novousmansky municipality
Lipetsk Oblast	Terbunsky municipality	Voronezh Oblast	Olkhovatsky municipality
Lipetsk Oblast	Usmansky municipality	Voronezh Oblast	Ostrogzhsky municipality
Lipetsk Oblast	Volovsky municipality	Voronezh Oblast	Paninsky municipality
Lipetsk Oblast	Yeletsky municipality	Voronezh Oblast	Pavlovsky municipality
Lipetsk Oblast	Zadonsky municipality	Voronezh Oblast	Petropavlovsky municipality
Orel Oblast	Bolkhovsky municipality	Voronezh Oblast	Podgorensky municipality
Orel Oblast	city of Livna	Voronezh Oblast	Povorinsky municipality
Orel Oblast	city of Mtsensk	Voronezh Oblast	Ramonsky municipality
Orel Oblast	city of Oryol	Voronezh Oblast	Repievsky municipality
Orel Oblast	Dmitrovsky municipality	Voronezh Oblast	Rossoshansky municipality
Orel Oblast	Dolzhansky municipality	Voronezh Oblast	Semiluksky municipality
Orel Oblast	Glazunovsky municipality	Voronezh Oblast	Talovsky municipality
Orel Oblast	Khotynetsky municipality	Voronezh Oblast	Ternovsky municipality
Orel Oblast	Kolpnyansky municipality	Voronezh Oblast	Verkhnehavsky municipality
Orel Oblast	Korsakovsky municipality	Voronezh Oblast	Verkhnemamonsky municipality
Orel Oblast	Krasnozorensky municipality	Voronezh Oblast	Vorobyevskiy municipality
Orel Oblast	Kromskoy municipality	Yaroslavl Oblast	Bolshesel'sky municipality
Orel Oblast	Livensky municipality	Yaroslavl Oblast	Borisoglebsky municipality
Orel Oblast	Maloarkhangelsky municipality	Yaroslavl Oblast	Breitovsky municipality
Orel Oblast	Mtsensky municipality	Yaroslavl Oblast	city of Pereslavl
Orel Oblast	Novoderevenkovsky municipality	Yaroslavl Oblast	city of Rybinsk
Orel Oblast	Novosilsky municipality	Yaroslavl Oblast	city of Yaroslavl
Orel Oblast	Orlovsky municipality	Yaroslavl Oblast	Danilovsky municipality

Name of the region of the Russian Federation	Name of the municipality	Name of the region of the Russian Federation	Name of the municipality
Orel Oblast	Pokrovsky municipality	Yaroslavl Oblast	Gavrilov Yamsky municipality
Orel Oblast	Shablykinsky municipality	Yaroslavl Oblast	Lyubimsky municipality
Orel Oblast	Soskovsky municipality	Yaroslavl Oblast	Myshkinsky municipality
Orel Oblast	Sverdlovsky municipality	Yaroslavl Oblast	Nekouzsky municipality
Orel Oblast	Trosniansky municipality	Yaroslavl Oblast	Nekrasovsky municipality
Orel Oblast	Uritsky municipality	Yaroslavl Oblast	Pereslavlsky municipality
Orel Oblast	Verkhovsky municipality	Yaroslavl Oblast	Pervomaisky municipality
Orel Oblast	Zalegoschensky municipality	Yaroslavl Oblast	Poshekhonsky municipality
Orel Oblast	Znamensky municipality	Yaroslavl Oblast	Rostovsky municipality
		Yaroslavl Oblast	Rybinsk municipality
		Yaroslavl Oblast	Tutaevsky municipality
		Yaroslavl Oblast	Uglichsky municipality
		Yaroslavl Oblast	Yaroslavsky municipality

Table 2. Data description: variable name, unit of measure, mean values and standard deviation of variables, data source.

No	Indicators	Units of Measure	Mean Values	Standart Deviation	Source
1	Name of the region of the Russian Federation				
2	Name of the municipality within the region				
3	Year				
4	Population as of January 1 of the current year	people	43517,1	86454,2	https://www.gks.ru/dbscripts/munst/
5	Total population under working age as of 1 January of the current year	people (aged 0–14 years)	6216,4	11706,3	https://www.gks.ru/dbscripts/munst/
6	Percentage of population under working age as of 1 January of the current year	%	15,7	1,5	calculated by authors
7	Number of arrivals	people	1136,4	2021,2	https://www.gks.ru/dbscripts/munst/
8	Number of dropouts	people	1107,5	1591,5	https://www.gks.ru/dbscripts/munst/
9	Migration inflow rate	arrivals per 10 000 inhabitants of the municipality concerned	301,5	161,0	calculated by authors
10	Migration growth rate	persons per 10 000 people of the population of the municipality concerned	-35,5	106,9	calculated by authors
11	Residential houses in the territory of the municipality put into operation	square meters of total area	20074,0	54644,0	https://www.gks.ru/dbscripts/munst/
12	Residential houses on the territory of the municipality per capita put into operation	square meters of total area per 10 000 inhabitants of the municipality concerned	3430,0	3608,4	calculated by authors
13	Income of the local budget actually executed	thousand rubles	8322134,0	46849860,0	https://www.gks.ru/dbscripts/munst/

№	Indicators	Units of Measure	Mean Values	Standart Deviation	Source
14	Consumer price index for goods and services	%	108,6	3,0	http://old.gks.ru/wps/wcm/connect/rosstat_main/rosstat/ru/statistics/publications/catalog/doc_1138623506156
15	Income of the local budget actually executed, modified to 2010 prices	thousand rubles	7677755,3	43213978,3	calculated by authors
16	Income of the local budget per capita, actually executed, modified to 2010 prices	thousand rubles per 10 000 population of the corresponding municipality	514191,2	1219384,9	calculated by authors
17	Investments in fixed assets (excluding budget funds) per person	rubles	24946,0	55879,2	https://www.gks.ru/dbscripts/munst/
18	Volume of investments in fixed assets (excluding budget funds) per person, modified to 2010 prices	rubles	23022,2	51827,8	calculated by authors
19	Average monthly salary of employees of organizations	rubles	4479,8	20811,0	https://www.gks.ru/dbscripts/munst/
20	Average monthly salary of employees of organizations, modified to 2010 prices	rubles	19020,3	4146,1	calculated by authors
21	Average number of employees of organizations	people	9099,3	21801,4	https://www.gks.ru/dbscripts/munst/
22	Average number of employees per capita in organizations	persons per 10 000 people of the population of the municipality concerned	1765,6	598,1	calculated by authors
23	The shortest distance from the geographical center of the municipality to Moscow by road	kilometers	420,6	157,0	https://maps.googleapis.com/maps/api/distancematrix/

№	Indicators	Units of Measure	Mean Values	Standard Deviation	Source
24	The shortest distance from the geographical center of the municipality to Moscow by road	minutes by car	323,3	107,5	https://maps.googleapis.com/maps/api/distancematrix/
25	The shortest distance from the geographical center of the municipality to the capital of the subject by road	kilometers	118,1	83,3	https://maps.googleapis.com/maps/api/distancematrix/
26	The shortest distance from the geographical center of the municipality to the capital of the subject by road	minutes by car	94,2	63,6	https://maps.googleapis.com/maps/api/distancematrix/

Source: compiled by the authors.